

Research article

Lexical forms and their distribution of the word for ‘tomorrow’ in Yunnan Tibetan

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Abstract: This article examines the word forms for ‘tomorrow’ in Khams Tibetan varieties of Yunnan, China, identifying three types: Type A, corresponding to Literary Tibetan (LT) *sang nyin*; Type B, corresponding to LT *nangs par*; and Type C, of unclear origin. Type A is the most widespread, Type B was geographically restricted, and Type C was isolated from the Melung dialect. This discussion focuses on the sound forms of Types A and B. The mBalhag dialect and Melung subgroup indicate a distinctive lexical distribution that separates the Type A areas. Furthermore, Type A shared irregular sound change in the nasal initial.*

Keywords: Tibetic; Khams Tibetan; lexical distribution; expansion; syllabic restructure

1. Introduction

This article describes word forms for ‘tomorrow’ in Khams Tibetan varieties in the Tibetosphere of Yunnan Province (henceforth, Yunnan Tibetan), and then examines how they are distributed from a geolinguistic viewpoint. According to Tournadre and Suzuki (2023:823), five word forms for ‘tomorrow’ are mainly utilised in Tibetic languages: *sang nyin* ‘tomorrow’, *nangs par* ‘tomorrow’ (originally meaning ‘in the morning’, *nangs kha* ‘tomorrow’ (originally meaning ‘early morning time’), *nangs dkar* ‘tomorrow’ (originally meaning ‘daybreaking time’), and *tho rengs* ‘tomorrow’ (originally meaning ‘dawn’) in Literary Tibetan (LT). Notably, a lexical relationship between ‘tomorrow’ and ‘morning’ is cross-linguistically attested, as in Japanese (*asita* ‘tomorrow’; Classical Japanese meaning ‘morning’), Chinese (*mingzhao* ‘next morning, tomorrow’; see Iwata 2009), German (*morgen* ‘tomorrow’; *Morgen* ‘morning’),

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Norwegian (*i morgen* ‘tomorrow’; *morgen* ‘morning’), and Burmese (*manakphyan* ‘tomorrow’; *manak* ‘morning’).

In Yunnan Tibetan, *sang nyin* is widely used, with some phonetic modifications or derivational changes. However, etymological information on the form *sang nyin* is unknown. A syllable-by-syllable analysis is yet to be conducted. However, based on derivational morphology, the first syllable *sang* is also used in words, such as *sang nub* ‘tomorrow evening’ and *sang lo* ‘next year’, and can therefore be considered to be a core semantic part of ‘the next time unit after the reference point’.

Prior to discussing the forms of ‘tomorrow’ in Yunnan Tibetan, Figure 1 presents the most recent dialectal classification of these varieties (Suzuki forthcoming; based on Suzuki 2022b, 2024a). Yunnan Tibetan is comprised of four groups: Sems-kyi-nyila, sDerong-nJol, Chaphreng, and Southern Route. This region is in the south-eastern corner of the Tibetosphere, where other ethnic languages are spoken in contact with Tibetic (see Roche and Suzuki 2018).

Legend: Sems-kyi-nyila: black symbols; sDerong-nJol: orange symbols; Chaphreng: skyblue symbols; Southern Route: green symbols.

Fig. 1 Classification of Yunnan Tibetan.

2. Word forms

Three types of word forms for ‘tomorrow’ are distinguished in the target varieties: Type A, *sang nyin* and its derivational forms; Type B, *nangs par*; and Type C, /'naw nɛ:/. These three forms are classified as follows:

Type A: equivalents to LT *sang nyin*

A1: /ŋ/ as the second syllable’s initial (e.g., /'s^hɔ̃ ŋĩ/, /'s^hɔ̃ ŋə/, and /'t^hɔ̃ ŋĩ/).

A2: /n/ as the second syllable’s initial (e.g., /'s^hɔ̃ nə/).

A3: /m/ as the second syllable’s initial (e.g., /'s^hɔ̃ mo/).

Type B: equivalents to LT *nangs par*

B1: /n/ as the first syllable’s initial (e.g., /^hnɔŋ^mbe:/).

B2: /l/ as the first syllable’s initial (e.g., /'lɔ̃^mbje:/).

Type C

/'naw nɛ:/ only.

Within each type, word forms are further classified according to the initial of the second syllable. Type A1 indicates a direct sound correspondence with the LT form, featuring a prepalatal nasal. Even with an initial /t^h/ in the first syllable, it is a regular sound correspondence (cf. Suzuki 2013, 2025). Type A2 contains a denti-alveolar nasal, which is a remarkable sound correspondence; in Yunnan Tibetan, some other words (e.g., LT *gnang nyin* ‘day after tomorrow’; *gnyis* ‘two’) exhibit a similar phenomenon. Type A3 includes a labial nasal and does not have a straightforward sound correspondence with the LT form. However, it is noteworthy that the word for ‘two’ (LT *gnyis*) exhibits a /m/-initial in a limited varieties of Yunnan Tibetan (Suzuki 2018, 2022a).

The difference between Types B1 and B2 lies in the initial of the first syllable. According to the LT form, B1 is an ordinary form, and B2 is an irregular form formed by the interchangeability of sounds [n] and [l]. This phonetic phenomenon has been observed in spoken varieties along the Jinshajiang River in the Tibetosphere of Yunnan (cf. Suzuki 2021). However, the single variety with Type B2, Zhollam, does not exhibit this sound interchange in its phonology.

Type C is apparently related to LT *gnam nas*, which does not exist in lexical form but can be interpreted as ‘from the sky’. Similar forms are not used in surrounding languages, such as Lisu and Naxi, where the word form for ‘tomorrow’ is /fa⁵⁵ gur³³/ (Weixi dialect; Mu and Sun 2012:158) and /so²¹ŋi³³/ (Sanba dialect; He 2015:407), respectively.

3. Geographical distribution and its analyses

Figure 2 illustrates the geographical distribution of types A, B, and C of the word forms described in Section 2. Type A is the most widespread type, whereas Types B and C are geographically characterised.

Fig. 2 Word forms for ‘tomorrow’, classified by types.

Types B and C are found to the south of the map in Weixi County. They are used in varieties of the Melung group (in a narrow sense, except for Phongpa) of Sems-kyi-

nyila Tibetan. The varieties spoken in Tacheng Town, where the circle and square symbols are in contact, use different types of word forms for ‘tomorrow’ depending on the dialectal group (Figure 1): Type A is used by varieties belonging to the mBrugpalung subgroup, while Type B, by varieties belonging to the Melung group. Word forms do not have any mutual influence beyond the subdialectal groups. Another variety of the Melung group, Phongpa, employs Type A, forming a geographical continuum of the area of Type A. Given the position of the Phongpa dialect, its use of Type A has replaced Type B, a form common to the Melung group, through a borrowing process from a neighbouring variety. In summary, Types B and C appear on the fringes of the Tibetic-speaking area.

Type B is also present in isolation in mBalhag. Based on Figure 2 this is inexplicable. However, the lexical specificity of mBalhag has been reported for other word forms, such as ‘yesterday’ (Suzuki 2024c) and ‘two’ (Suzuki 2018). Of these, Figure 2 and the example of ‘two’ exhibits the lexical commonality with the Melung group. Despite the ambiguity of the migration history of mBalhag Tibetans (see Suzuki 2013), it is possible that mBalhag and Melung are related, although their affiliations differ at the group level: sDerong-nJol and Sems-kyi-nyila (see Figure 1). Considering that the distribution of Type B is peripheral, the use of LT *nangs par* can be analysed in an archaic form.

Type C occurs only in Melung, which is located at the southernmost point of Weixi County (Yongchun Township). As noted in Section 2, the form is neither equivalent to LT nor borrowed. However, an alternative hypothesis is posited herewith. Based on its geographical location, language affiliation, and the locals’ migration history that they are descendants of migrants from the western half of Tacheng Town (the area of Type B), the form of Type C /’naw ne:/ can be analysed as a variant of Type B: naw ne: < *nam ne: < *naŋ me: < *naŋ^mbe: < nŋ^mbe: (Type B1), equivalent to LT *nangs par*. In this hypothesised process, the assimilation of the prenasal part ^mb > m is often observed in several varieties of Yunnan Tibetan (e.g., Suzuki 2009, 2016). Another key sound change m > n is less attested, and here the process is combined with an intersyllabic change, the labialisation of the final of the preceding syllable (ŋ > m) with a dissimilation of the following initial (m > n). Although this hypothesis is not sufficiently supported, the distribution of Type C suggests this possibility.

Figure 3 shows the sub-classification of Types A and B. Distribution of each subtype is discussed below.

Fig. 3 Word forms for ‘tomorrow’, classified by subtypes.

Type A is further subdivided into three types based on the initial of the second syllable. Among these, Type A1 is the most widespread, whereas Types A2 and A3 are minorities. Type A2 is distributed in parts of the Jinshajiang River water system, including the main stream and its tributaries, the mBrugpalung (Zhubalong) River and the Laphu (Lapu) River. As discussed above, the Type A2 varieties in Tacheng Town belong to a different dialect group than those with Type B1, and this boundary is reflected in other lexical items. Therefore, the question arises regarding its northern part, which is in contact with the Type A1 area. Type A3 is isolated (Phongpa dialect, belonging to the same subgroup as Types B and C), as shown in Figure 3.

Type B is further divided into two types based on the initial of the first syllable. Type B1 includes two areas: mThachu and mBalhag. According to the geographical distribution, the two are not closely related. Type B2 (Zholam dialect) is isolated between Type B1 (Gongnong dialect) and Type C (Melung dialect). Each language community is not directly connected to the others and retains some degree of independence. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that Type B2 developed independently from the varieties of Type B1 owing to its remote location.

We examine the basis for subclassifying Type A. The central subtype appears to be a recently developed form with an ABA (concentric) distribution, though this pattern is not confirmed in this present study. Some examples exhibit a distribution similar to Type A2. For example, the distribution of the initial form of the word for ‘two’ (LT *gnyis*) is closely related to (but not identical to) that of Types A2 and A3 (Suzuki 2018:39-40). This LT word form includes an initial *ny*, which usually corresponds to a prepalatal nasal /ɲ/ in most Tibetic languages. However, most varieties with Type A2 exhibit a denti-alveolar nasal /n/ for ‘two’. The same applies to Type A3, as Phongpa uses a bilabial nasal /m/ for ‘two’. However, the reverse is not true. Not all varieties with /n/ or /m/ for the word for ‘two’ exhibit Types A2 and A3, respectively. Recognising the relationship between ‘two’ and ‘tomorrow’ in the initial consonant would mean that Type A has expanded and replaced Types A2 and A3. Varieties belonging to the Nysishe and mBrugpalung subgroups would possess Type A2, whereas varieties belonging to the Lancangjiang subgroup would possess Type A3.

Type A2 is concentrated in the Jinshajiang River water system. This pattern of distribution is also attested in other words, such as ‘yesterday’ (Suzuki 2024c) and ‘nineteen’ (Suzuki forthcoming). Type A2 varieties are part of the rGyalthagic subgroup of Sems-kyi-nyila Tibetan (Suzuki 2024a, b) and are the only varieties that display characteristic lexical features. This suggests the existence of another stratum in addition to Sems-kyi-nyila Tibetan.

4. Conclusion

This article examined the lexical forms of ‘tomorrow’ in Tibetic languages in the Tibetosphere of Yunnan. All the varieties employ a word equivalent to LT *sang nyin* ‘tomorrow’ (Type A) and *nangs par* ‘tomorrow; in the morning’ (Type B), except for a single variety (Melung) using /‘naw nɛ:/ (Type C). Types A and B were further classified into subgroups based on their phonological features. The article argues that variation within Type A relates to the phonological form of the word for ‘two’. It proposes that Type A1 has expanded and replaced Types A2 and A3, based on

comparison with the form for ‘two’. Additionally, the form for ‘tomorrow’ suggests the presence of a substratum in varieties spoken along the Jinshajiang River.

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